

Towards Intelligent Cultural Adaptation of Educational Technology: An exploratory study

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Abstract. This paper describes an exploratory study in the area of cultural differences to inform the design of educational technology. The objective of this work was to investigate the role of Hofstede's cultural dimensions as a framework to understand cultural traits of undergraduate students at the College of Informatics, University of Veracruz, Mexico. The methodology consisted of collecting information from a pool of 65 students considering cultural, motivational orientation and learning styles information and performing segmentation analyses to group the data into profiles. The resulting profiles use motivational orientation and learning styles as variables that explain cultural characteristics for these learners. This study serves two purposes: on the one hand, the profiles can be employed as rationale for the development of culturally adaptive learning technology. On the other it paves the way for the understanding of cultural variations and how these can be investigated in relation to educational technology.

Resumen. Este artículo describe un estudio exploratorio de las diferencias culturales para informar el diseño de tecnología educativa. El objetivo de este trabajo fue investigar el rol que las dimensiones culturales de Hofstede como marco referencial para entender matices culturales entre estudiantes de licenciatura en la Facultad de Informática, Universidad Veracruzana, México. La metodología consistió de la colecta de información entre 65 estudiantes considerando orientación cultural, motivacionales y estilo de aprendizaje así como la realización de un análisis de segmentación para agrupar la información en perfiles de estudiantes. Los perfiles resultantes

usan la orientación motivacional y los estilos de aprendizaje como variables que explican características culturales de los estudiantes. Este estudio sirve dos propósitos: por un lado, los perfiles pueden ser usados como base lógica para el desarrollo de tecnología educativa culturalmente adaptativa. Por otro lado, facilitará el entendimiento de variaciones culturales y como estas pueden ser investigadas en relación a la tecnología educativa.

Introduction

Cultural variation in students could provide criteria to underpin intelligent adaptation of learning technology. Intelligent Adaptation refers to Artificial Intelligence techniques that deal with problems pertaining the provision of specific information as required by individuals instead of offering generic responses to a population. In this sense, adaptation of learning technology refers to software facilities that decide the type of content individual students will receive. The rationale for these decisions is often a criterion in connection with learner's characteristics.

This paper presents preliminary results in the area of cultural traits of undergraduate students that could inform the redesign of learning objects for first year introduction to programming. The research question pertaining this research is: How could cultural differences be understood to inform the design of adaptive learning technology? To explore the question, Hofstede's [1] framework was employed to investigate whether the cultural dimensions could be explained in terms of educational variables such as motivational orientation and learning styles. The objective is to provide evidence towards understanding cultural variability that may be employed to underpin cultural adaptation in learning technology. This research departs from the concept of culturally adaptable learning objects [6] to present a theoretical background, the methodology and the results of this research. In the discussion and future work sections, some pointers are given that establish a research path to re-design and evaluate the resulting learning technology.

Background

The use of cultural elements to inform the design of educational technology is a topic that has received increased attention because cultural attributes might affect learner's attitudes and perceptions. Hofstede's previous work [2,3,4,5] provides a starting point to explore cultural variation and its probable role and influence in the learning process. Hofstede [2] defines culture as a "collective programming" that distinguishes a group of people from another. This collective programming is normally associated to regions or countries and provides an interesting standing point to explore learners' attitudes to learning. According to Hofstede, [2] this collective programming is imprinted in the brain and can be observed only when the peoples from one particular group behave similarly under similar circumstances because implicit rules and norms predispose group members to behave in a particular way to known circumstances. According to Hofstede's theory, cultural variation can be explained with a set of five variables or dimensions: Power Distance Index (PDI), Uncertainty Avoidance Index (UAI), Individualism (IND), Masculinity (MAS) and Long Term Orientation. Hofstede define the cultural dimensions as:

- Power Distance Index (PDI) refers to ease with which less powerful people accept power disparity between. Hofstede suggests that power disparity is accepted both by more and less powerful people in a particular society.
- Individuality (IND) refers to the bonds existing between the members of a given society. Its opposite is collectivism and expresses the degree to which members of a group define themselves as part of a group.
- Masculinity (MAS) defines the preference for values such as competition and the acquisition of material possessions as indicator of success. Its opposite indicates a group's preference for values associated to the promotion of the quality of life among the group members.
- Uncertainty Avoidance Index (UAI) is the degree of tolerance that a

group of people has towards uncertainty and ambiguity. The UAI also describes the comfort felt by the group members to new and unexpected situations. Rigid cultures tend to minimize uncertainty by establishing strict rules and laws and tending to believe in absolute truths and tend to be more emotional.

- Long Term Orientation (LTO) refers to the preference for values associated to longer term gain such as saving and perseverance. This cultural dimension was not employed in the current study because Hofstede's latest results [5] for the culture of interest could be used as benchmark against which the results of this study could be compared.

Further studies devised by Hofstede, evidences the relation between some dimensions such as power distance index and individualism given that groups of people with higher individualism have a smaller power distance index and vice versa. Hofstede's evidence for the "collective programming" that defines groups has been collected mainly in big multinational corporations [3, 4, 5] which is a very different setting to education. Some studies based on Hofstede's cultural dimensions present evidence that a cultural characteristic (power distance) plays a role on how learners perform and persist in online learning environments [7]. It has also been suggested that students from collectivistic cultures are less motivated to participate in online learning courses than those from individualistic cultures and that students from ambiguity intolerant cultures might be less motivated to participate than their counterparts [8].

The attractiveness of utilizing culture in the design of technology-enhanced learning environments lies in the possibility to alter presentation elements (language variations, examples, styles, motivation style) to match users' culture as opposed to be a reflection of the designers' culture. Arguably, existing educational technology (i.e. tutoring systems) could, inadvertently reflect goals beliefs and/or expectations originated in one culture and could or could not be

shared by end users in a different culture. Furthermore, it would be desirable that educational technology be endowed with elements to automatically adjust its content delivery considering the cultural background of individual users [6]. While this proposition is attractive to intelligent educational technology designers, culture is a topic difficult to conceptualize and implement as rationale for adaptation.

The work of Hofstede [1] provides a starting point for the understanding of cultural variation. While Hofstede's work relates to values in business environments, it provides a framework that is applicable to teaching and learning. Hofstede's five cultural dimensions are relevant in academic settings because many students' values, such as motivation and learning orientation, could be related to them. To explore the role of motivation and learning styles, two other measures were considered on this study: Harter's motivational orientation [10] questionnaire and Kolb's learning styles inventory [11]. These scales were selected, as they are typical to academic environments and could be valued differently supporting Hofstede's idea of cultural differences. Harter's questionnaire [10] consists of five subscales each related to an aspect of motivation. Responses to individual subscales provide an idea of the learner's orientation (intrinsic or extrinsic) for that subscale. The subscales are 1. preference for challenge vs. preference for easy work, 2. curiosity/interest vs. pleasing teacher/getting grades, 3. independent mastery vs. dependence on teacher, 4. independent judgment vs. reliance on teachers' judgment and 5. internal criteria vs. external criteria.

Kolb's learning styles inventory [11] works on two levels: the first level consists of four orientations that when combined (second level) can be used to describe individual student's styles that reflect preferences on managing education, decision-making, and problem solving in the classroom. Before defining the learning style, Kolb's questionnaire [11] established the students' preferences for four orientations (first level): Concrete Experience (CE), Reflexive Observation (RO), Abstract Conceptualization (AC) and Active

Experimentation (AE). These orientations are then combined to produce four learning styles: Diverging (CE/RO), Assimilating (AC/RO), Converging (AC/AE) and Accommodating (CE/AE).

Methodology

The methodology consisted of utilizing existing instruments to collect data from the target population and analyze the results. Both, Harter's questionnaire [10] and Kolb's inventory [11] were adapted so that the questions referred to students' characteristics for the introduction to programming class. The data collected was analyzed using correlations and further analyzed using segmentation analyses to procure a set of four styles.

Instruments

The instruments underwent an adaptation so that the questions were expressed in the area of study (first year introduction to programming) and phrased in Spanish. Hofstede's instrument consists of a series of 26 questions (6 for demographics and five related to each of the cultural dimensions). All the questions are scored individually on a five-point scale (strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, strongly agree). The motivation self-report was an adaptation of Harter's test [10] with five subscales that represent characteristics associated to either intrinsic or extrinsic motivation. The scale consisted of thirty questions, six questions per subscales, the subscales are preference for challenge vs. preference for easy work, curiosity/interest vs. pleasing teacher/getting grades, independent mastery vs. dependence on teacher, independent judgment vs. reliance on teachers' judgment and internal criteria vs. external criteria.. The questions were alternated and prompted the student to indicate the degree (in a scale from 1 to 4) to which that aspect is true or less true for that student. The original subscales were adapted to determine the motivational orientation of the learner towards the class of interest since the original scale [10] consists of

generic questions.

Finally, Kolb's test [11] was employed to assess students' learning style in the class of interest. The test consisted of nine sections asking the student for the degree to which he or she adheres to one of four stages of the learning process. Each question could be answered with a Likert-type scale (1-4). The resulting instruments were tested for internal consistency in a pilot test to estimate the reliability of test scores. The pilot (N=28) indicated internal consistency estimates as for Hofstede's (Alpha = .635), Harter's (Alpha = .861) and Kolb's (Alpha = .973). These results indicate good reliability for Hofstede's adaptation and very good reliability for both Harter's and Kolb's adaptations.

Population and data collection

The population for this study consisted of 65 students between the ages of 18 and 23 years old. There were 44 male and 21 female undergraduate students, all of whom had previously taken or were taking the class of interest in the semester from February to August 2010 at the College of Informatics, University of Veracruz, México. The students all consented to answer the three questionnaires and take part in this experiment. The students answered the questionnaires individually via a web page in an average of 20 minutes. The answers provided by the students were automatically stored in an online database.

Analyses

The analyses consisted of calculating the degree to which this population of students could be defined considering Hofstede's dimensions. Analyses were also performed individually to determine the type of motivational orientation and learning styles associated to each of the students of the sample. To determine the population's index for Hofstede's cultural dimensions, the following formulas were used: $PDI = 35m(03) + 35m(06) + 25m(14) - 20m(17)$; $UAI = 25m(13) + 20m(16) - 50m(18) - 15m(19) + 120$; $IDV = -50m(01) + 30m(02) -$

$20m(04) - 25m(08) + 130$; $MAS = 60m(05) - 20m(07) + 20m(15) - 70m(20) + 100$, where $m(X)$ is the mean score for question X. To assess whether students' motivation was intrinsic or extrinsic, individual responses to the adaptation of Harter's questionnaire [10] were analyzed. Answers to the questions related to individual subscales were averaged out to determine the pole towards which an individual student was more oriented. For example, questions 4, 9, 14, 19, 24 and 29 were related to subscale 4 (Independent judgment vs. reliance on teachers' judgment). Lower scores relate to the extrinsic motivation pole of this subscale (i.e. reliance on teacher's judgment) whereas higher scores relate to the intrinsic motivation pole (i.e. independent judgment). Finally, to analyze the learning style associated to individual learners a computation of the scores associated to the learning process (CE, RO, AC, AE) was performed. Depending on the value for each learning process, individual learners could be allocated to one of four learning style representing the combination of two preferred styles as indicated in the background section. For example, if a student scored high in CE and RO, this student was considered as having a diverging learning style. Subsequent analyses were carried out to study the relations between the different variables of interest using correlations and segmentation analyses.

Results

Hofstede's indexes for this population were calculated as follows: $PDI = -13.69$, $UAI = 53.15$, $IDV = 56$, $MAS = 45.70$. The values associated to the cultural dimension could be negative as in the case of PDI for this sample, indicating a decreased perception of inequality between students and teacher in the classroom, Table 1. As can be seen in Table 1, the results indicate that this group of students tends to be slightly more intrinsically than extrinsically motivated. This suggests students would prefer to work for their interest and learning rather than for rewards or recognition.

Subscale 1		Subscale 2		Subscale 3		Subscale 4		Subscale 5	
M	SD								
2.36	0.55	2.78	0.38	2.27	0.48	2.39	0.54	2.59	0.52

Table 1. Results of Harter's (1981) subscales

Finally, regarding the learning styles the majority of this population (63%, 41 out of 65 students) was classified as divergent or students who have inclinations to concrete experience (CE) and reflexive observation (RO). 17% of the students (11 out of 65) can be defined as Accommodating or having preference for Active Experimentation (AE) and Concrete Experience (CE). 15% of the population (10 out of 65) fell in the fourth quadrant indicating an Assimilating learning style associated to abstract conceptualization (AC) and reflexive observation (RO).

Figure 1. Results considering Kolb's learning styles

Finally, only 5% of the students (3 out of 65) can be identified as having a Converging learning style related to Abstract Conceptualization (AC) and Active Experimentation (AE) see Figure 1. Since the objective of this study was to investigate whether Hofstede's cultural dimensions could help understand how particular populations could be categorized, a series of correlations were performed, see Table 2.

	Subscale 1	Subscale 2	Subscale 3	Subscale 4	Subscale 5
PDI	-.1328 p=.291	-.1332 p=.290	.0518 p=.682	.0660 p=.602	-.1881 p=.133
UAI	-.2234 p=.074	-.2618 p=.035*	.0162 p=.898	-.1509 p=.230	-.0735 p=.561
IDV	.2548 p=.041*	-.1186 p=.347	.0427 p=.736	.0130 p=.918	-.0331 p=.794
MAS	.0472 p=.709	-.1518 p=.227	.2426 p=.052	-.1641 p=.192	.2696 p=.030*

Table 2. Correlations, Hofstede's cultural dimensions and Harter's motivation (* $p < .05$)

As observed in Table 2, there are 3 significant correlations. The first positively correlates individualism (IDV) with subscale 1 (preference for challenge vs. preference for easy work); this result suggests students who are more individualistic tend to be more intrinsically motivated. The second is a negative correlation between Uncertainty Avoidance Index (UAI) and Subscale 2 (curiosity/interest vs. pleasing teacher/getting grades); this correlation suggests students who score high on the uncertainty avoidance scale tend to be more extrinsically motivated. The third is a positive correlation between the masculinity index (MAS) and Subscale 5 (internal criteria vs. external criteria); this result suggests students who scored higher on the masculinity index also have more intrinsic motivation.

To further explore the data, a segmentation analyses was performed to define user profiles that could be used to describe this particular population. The styles could be used to predict important behaviors based on Hofstede's cultural dimensions. The approach taken was that of Automatic Interaction Detection (AID) [12]. A segmentation tree was generated dividing the population into

homogeneous segments with respect to a response variable. The aim of defining segmentation trees is to divide a population in homogeneous segments with respect to a variable of interest. To achieve that, it is necessary to 1) group the categories of the variables to analyze, 2) consider all the population and assume all variables have a chance to occur and 3) add up partial probabilities taken from each categories. Given the interest on cultural aspects, the response variables were Hofstede's cultural dimensions and its relation to the independent variables (learning styles and type of motivation).

To segment the population, three categories were defined for the response variables considering individual scores: low (< -75) medium (≥ -75 a ≤ 75) and high (>75). Segmentations trees were formed considering these segments and grouping students by learning style first and by type of motivation later see Figures 2, 3, 4 and 5. As a result, four profiles were identified for this particular population:

- Profile 1: Medium IDV, divergent student with either preference for challenge (intrinsic) or preference for easy work (extrinsic).
- Profile 2: High IDV, divergent student with preference for challenge (intrinsic).
- Profile 3: Medium to high UAI, divergent students with preference to learn because of curiosity.
- Profile 4: Medium to high MAS, divergent student with high internal criteria

Figure 2. Segmentation analyses for Profile 1: IDV explained by divergent learning style and preference for challenge or preference for easy work motivation orientation

Figure 3. Segmentation analyses for Profile 2: IDV explained by divergent learning style and challenging motivation orientation.

Figure 4. Segmentation analyses for UAI explained by divergent learning style and curiosity motivation orientation

Figure 5. Segmentation analyses for UAI explained by divergent learning style and curiosity type motivation

Discussions and future work

The objective of this paper was to explore the suitability to use Hofstede's cultural dimensions as a means to understand cultural traits of a Mexican population of undergraduate students. Although Hofstede [9] provides an indication of the cultural traits for business-oriented contexts in Mexico, there are not studies for an academic environment. Thus, it was interesting to see 1) whether these cultural dimensions could be used to understand behaviors in an academic setting and 2) whether cultural behaviors could be described in terms of academic independent variables. Perhaps not surprisingly, a marked difference was found between the results of this study and the results provided in Hofstede's study in business settings [9]. Hofstede's original study reported the following results: PDI = 81, UAI = 82, IDV = 30 and MAS = 69. There are two possible explanations or their combined effects that might explain the discrepancies between the results: in terms of the context and/or in terms of the time elapsed since Hofstede's study. The most striking difference between the two sets of data relates to PDI. It was expected that in an academic setting, students would perceive the distance between the teacher and themselves in similar terms to that found by Hofstede. Surprisingly, this study found that students scored very low in this cultural dimension (PDI = -13.69) suggesting a perception of equality in their relationship with their teachers. Another surprising difference was noted in the IDV dimension as it was expected students would be less individualistic as Hofstede found (IDV=30); however, these students scored higher in this study (IDV=56). This difference could be due to the generational gap between Hofstede's original study in 1982 and the undergraduate students who participated in this study in 2010.

In order to investigate whether these cultural dimensions were correlated to typical variables in academic settings (motivational orientation and learning gains), a series of correlations were performed. There were three significant correlations between the cultural dimensions and Harter's subscales (see Table

1). The correlation indicate a) more individualistic students tend to prefer more challenges (intrinsic motivation) ($p < .05$); b) students who tend to avoid uncertainty in the class tend to please teachers (extrinsic motivation) ($p < .05$) and c) students with higher score in the MAS dimension depend more on internal criteria (intrinsic motivation) ($p < .05$). This last result might seem paradoxical given that the MAS dimension as define by Hofstede represents a behavior associated with competition and the look for recognition. However, in an academic setting, this might mean that students who know how to evaluate themselves would also bolster their successes by looking for external rewards or by competing with others.

To further investigate the relationships between the cultural dimension and the independent variables (motivation and learning styles), a segmentation analysis was performed. As a result, four profiles of students were defined considering the cultural behaviors of this particular population. The definition of these profiles represents a first step towards designing educational technology that could adapt automatically by responding to specific cultural traits of the students. Currently at the College of Informatics, University of Veracruz, a repository of Learning Objects exists and is available to introduction to programming students. It would be desirable that these objects could automatically adapt themselves to the student's learning style in a similar fashion to Amiel et al. LOCA paradigm [6].

The profiles described in this paper are a step towards automation, as it is possible to re-design the existing learning objects in the shape of the four profiles identified for this population. Adaptation would be possible, for example, if the learning object detects one particular student as belonging to one profile and provides the educational content accordingly. To that end, it is possible, for instance, to pre-screen students with a battery of tests. It could also be possible to investigate further and analyze student's behaviors for each profile to help in the implementation of automatic detection of student's profiles. An important concept to be taken into account is leverage obtained from exposing the learner

to non-preferred cultural orientation and learning styles so as to broaden the learners' capacities to work across a range of orientations and styles. The definition of Artificial Intelligence techniques such as neural networks or Bayesian networks, would allow for the automatic detection of behaviors and the calculation of success probabilities give a series of preferred learning styles while considering the learner's motivation. Subsequent studies will follow these directions.

Another direction to be taken will replicate the study reported on this paper in a different population of students in another region of Mexico and in a region of the South-Eastern United States. More importantly, future work will redesign and evaluate learning objects with four cultural traits for students at the University of Veracruz. An evaluation of this nature will shed light onto the effectiveness of adapting learning technology considering cultural variability.

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